

SELF-EFFICACY AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE OF SCHOOL TEACHERS: TEACHING EXPERIENCE WISE ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This study was designed to use a descriptive correlation design to examine the relationship between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers. All the school teachers (at primary, secondary and higher secondary level) of Tirunelveli District, Tamilnadu constituted the population for the purpose of the present study. The study was conducted on a sample of 650 school teachers drawn from 67 schools of Tirunelveli District. A stratified randomization technique of sampling was employed for collecting data. Two questionnaire forms were used to elicit the needed data for this study. One questionnaire named as, “Emotional Intelligence scale” which was constructed and validated by Hyde, Dhar, &Pethe, (2001) was used to collect the data. For collecting data on the variable of self-efficacy of teachers, second questionnaire named as “Teacher Self-efficacy Scale” by Ralf Schwarzer, Gerdamarie. S. Schmitz and Gary T. Daytner (1999) were used. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis was used to investigate the relationship between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers. Correlation analysis was showed the existence of statistically significant strong positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers who have teaching experience of 5 years and below 5 years. And also statistically significant moderate positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers who have teaching experience of above 5 years was apparent. The correlation analysis also showed the significant strong positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers.

Key words: Self-efficacy, Emotional Intelligence, School Teachers, Correlation design.

INTRODUCTION

The historic transition from industrial to the information era has profound implications for educational systems. In the past, youth who had little schooling had recourse to industrial and manufacturing jobs requiring little in the way of cognitive skills. Such options are rapidly shrinking. The new realities require cognitive and self-regulatory competencies to fulfill complex occupational roles and to manage the demands of contemporary life. Education has now become vital for an engaged and productive life. The rapid pace of technological change and accelerated growth of knowledge are placing a premium on capability for self-directed learning. Good schooling fosters psychological growth that contributes to the quality of life beyond the vocational domain. A major goal of formal education should be to equip students with intellectual tools, efficacy beliefs and intrinsic interests to educate themselves throughout their lifetime. These personal resources enable individuals to gain new knowledge and to cultivate skills either for their own sake or to better their lives. There are three principal ways in which efficacy beliefs operate as an important contributor to academic development. These include students beliefs in their efficacy to regulate their own learning and to master different academic subjects; teachers’ beliefs in their personal efficacy to motivate and promote learning their

students; and faculties collective sense of efficacy that their schools can accomplish significant academic progress [4].

SELF-EFFICACY

Efficacy beliefs affect the quality of emotional life and vulnerability to stress and depression. Although self-efficacy is a type of cognition, theory and research support the idea that it can affect other facets of development (e.g., social, emotional, behavioural) and that is influenced by various personal, social and contextual variables. Self-efficacy is grounded in the larger theoretical framework of social cognitive theory. This theory postulates that human functioning results from interactions among personal factors (e.g., cognitions, emotions), behaviours and environmental conditions. Self-efficacy refers to subjective judgments of one's capabilities to organize and execute courses of action to attain designated goals. It is a belief about what a person can do rather than personal judgments about one's physical or personality attributes [25]. Tscannen-Moran, Woolfolk Hoy (1998) developed a multi-disciplinary model of teacher self-efficacy. The four sources of efficacy lead to cognitive processing (thoughts, beliefs, values and assumptions). Then a teacher can both analyze the effectiveness of the teaching and learning via student achievement and assess the effectiveness of the teaching via teacher competence. The resulting data reveal the teachers' self efficacy. Essential to this process is the consequence of this revelation; now is the moment for the teacher to make changes to increase learning and achievement, enhance teaching and self-efficacy, and improve the schooling and curricular advancement. Teacher self-efficacy is defined as a teacher's confidence in his or her ability to affect and promote student learning [5].

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

In Guy Claxton's words: 'Learning itself is an intrinsically emotional business'. The process of learning in any context can involve struggle, frustration, thrill or excitement. In the public or formal context of the classroom, with all of the dynamics between teacher and learner and between learners, and with the perception that there is the prospect of success or failure, the potential for strong feelings is heightened. It follows that if the job of a teacher is to help their learners to learn, a teacher needs to be able to recognize the emotional dimension of learning and to work with it. Teachers need to use their emotional intelligence. Learners' perceptions can alter too when the teacher uses emotional intelligence. A well-developed self-awareness is the first step in being emotionally intelligent [17]. Emotionally intelligent teachers convey a sense of caring towards their learners. They create an emotional climate that enhances the learning environment, reduces peer conflict and facilitates a more desirable teaching context [8]. Emotional Intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth [19].

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Self-efficacy beliefs regulate human functioning through four major processes. They include cognitive, motivational, affective and selection process. The self-efficacy mechanism plays a pivot role in the self-regulation of affective states. One can distinguish three principal ways in which self-efficacy beliefs affect the nature and intensity of emotional experiences. Such beliefs create attention biases and influence how emotive life events are construed and cognitively represented; they operate in the exercise of control over perturbing thought patterns; and they sponsor courses of action that transform environments in ways that alter their emotive potential [22]. Teaching is an interpretative activity. Accuracy of emotional interpretation is one of the most fundamental attributes of the effective teacher. When emotional understanding is absent, emotional misunderstanding will take its place [20]. At the heart of Emotional Intelligence lies the ability to sustain an optimistic outlook in life, a healthy self-

esteem and qualities such as self-appreciation, self-respect, intuition, character, integrity and motivation. It includes good communication and relationship skills. Emotionally intelligent teachers are recognized by their happy disposition and optimism towards their profession and life in general. Emotionally intelligent teachers are efficient, considerate and conscious as they go about their teaching and daily interactions. They teach with an attitude of joy, harmony and co-operation [8]. Motivational concepts such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, self-efficacy and task involvement and ego involvement represent important antecedents of emotions. Several theorists have suggested that goals and motivation plays an important role in producing emotions. For instance, Mandler (1984) proposes that emotion results from goal blockages. For Ortony et al. (1988), emotions result from appraisals of events with reference to some goal. Perhaps Frijda (1988) said it best: Emotions arise in response to events that are important to the individuals' goals, motives, or concerns [12]. Self-efficacy gives teachers the confidence to effectively develop curriculum and respond to the social and emotional well-being of their students. Researchers claim that self-efficacy gives teachers the confidence to inspire their students to achieve their potential and increase their own teaching aspirations [5]. The ability to accurately recognize the emotions of others is essential for successful social functioning. An inability to recognize the facial expression of emotion perception can lead to inappropriate social responding and diminished social self-efficacy [13]. A recent meta-analysis of research reported a positive relationship between greater accuracy in emotion recognition and better work outcomes in occupations as diverse as physicians, medical interns, human service workers, foreign service officers, principals, school teachers and business executives [20]. Considering this as a backdrop a study was conducted to know the relationship between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to their teaching experience.

REVIEW OF RELEATED LITERATURE

[25] Wu, Yingying (2018) found that the total effect of EI on self-efficacy was .61, indicating that higher EI is positively correlated with a higher level of self-efficacy. This relationship was partially mediated by teaching performance. [1] A. Penrose et al. (2007) found that length of teaching experience and current status add significant direct effects on predicting teacher self efficacy but did not moderate the relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher self efficacy. These findings are significant as this now demonstrates a relationship between levels of emotional intelligence in teachers, their self efficacy beliefs and teacher effectiveness.[14] J. Parameswari(2013) found that emotional intelligence and self-efficacy are significantly related to each other.[2] Abdolvahabi, Zahra et al. (2012) found that emotional awareness, empathy, and problem solving components has a positive and significant relationship with self-efficacy in teaching practical course and the level of job self-efficacy, while there is no significant relation in other components.[11] Farhan, Sheeba&Zehra, Ali, Amena. (2016) found that Emotional Intelligence is not only correlated but also found to be a predictor of self-efficacy, life satisfaction and positive affect in teachers of public sector universities in Karachi, Pakistan. [10] Dehvari, Abdolmalek Mohammadi1 and Saravani, Reza, Mohammad(2015) found that self-efficacy has significant relationship with emotional intelligence and its subscales (Assessing emotions and Regulation emotions) at 95% confidence level.[3] Aurora Adina Colomeischia and Tudor Colomeischiaa(2014) found that good correlation between the teachers' emotional intelligence, the teachers' self-efficacy, the work mentality and their general work satisfaction.[18] Moutan, Alexandre et al. (2013) found that positive association between EI and self-efficacy, and more particularly that the sociability factor of EI predicted the TSES total score. Moreover, neither age nor teaching time experience was related to EI or self-efficacy scores. These results both confirm and extend previous findings on the association between EI and self-efficacy. [23] Shaukat, Sadia. (2016) found that significant differences were found on four subscales of emotional intelligence and two subscales of teacher self-efficacy with demographic variables (qualification, teaching status, teaching experience).

[21] Sahin, Harun. (2017) found that while some sub-dimensions of emotional intelligence (well-being, sociality and self-esteem) positively and significantly predict the pre-service teachers' self efficacy level, some other dimensions (self-control and emotionality) do not significantly predict the self-efficacy level.[7] Chan, David W.(2008) found that Intrapersonal emotional intelligence and interpersonal emotional intelligence were found to predict significantly active coping strategy, but teacher self-efficacy did not contribute independently to the prediction of active coping even though there was some evidence that teacher self-efficacy might interact with intrapersonal emotional intelligence in the prediction of active coping, especially for male teachers.A critical appraisal of above said reviewed studies revealed that there are some gaps on the relationship of Self-Efficacy and Emotional Intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience.

METHODOLOGY

POPULATION AND SAMPLE

All the teachers (secondary) of Rampur District, U.P.constituted the population for the purpose of the present study. The study was confined to both Government and Private (Management) school teachers.

The study was conducted on a sample of 120 teachers drawn from 12 schools of Rampur District (UP). A stratified randomization technique of sampling was employed for collecting the data. Out of all the senior secondary/ higher secondary schools of Rampur District, random selection of twelve schools was done.

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Quantitative approach is applied in this study. This study is designed to use a descriptive correlation design to examine the relationship between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers. All the school teachers (at primary, secondary and higher secondary level) of Tirunelveli District, Tamilnadu constituted the population for the purpose of the present study. The study was conducted on a sample of 650 school teachers drawn from 67 schools of Tirunelveli District. A stratified randomization technique of sampling was employed for collecting data. Two questionnaire forms were used to elicit the needed data for this study. One questionnaire named as, “Emotional Intelligence scale”which was constructed and validated by Hyde, Dhar, &Pethe, (2001) was used to collect the data. For collecting data on the variable of self-efficacy of teachers, second questionnaire named as Teacher Self-efficacy Scale by Ralf Schwarzer, Gerdamarie. S. Schmitz and Gary T. Daytner (1999) were used. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Analysis was used to investigate the relationship between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers.

H₀: 1 *There is no significant correlation exists between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience of 5 years and below 5 years.*

Table - 1

Correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience of 5 years and below 5 years

Variable	N	Emotional Intelligence
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		<i>r - Value</i>	<i>P – Value</i>
Self-Efficacy	650	0.765	0.000** S

** *Significant at 1% level*

It is inferred from the above table that the p value is lesser than 0.01 and hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is significant positive correlation exists between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience of 5 years and below 5 years. The Pearson correlation co-efficient for self-efficacy and emotional intelligence was found as 0.765 which indicates that both variables are strongly positively correlated.

H₀: 2 *There is no significant correlation exists between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience of above 5 years.*

Table – 1 Correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience of above 5 years

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	
		<i>r - Value</i>	<i>P – Value</i>
Self-Efficacy	650	0.674	0.000** S

** *Significant at 1% level*

It is inferred from the above table that the p value is lesser than 0.01 and hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is significant positive correlation exists between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers with regard to teaching experience of above 5 years. The Pearson correlation co-efficient for self-efficacy and emotional intelligence was found as 0.674 which indicates that both variables are moderately positively correlated.

H₀: 3 *There is no significant correlation exists between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers.*

Table – 1 Correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers

<i>Variable</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	
		<i>r - Value</i>	<i>P - Value</i>
Self-Efficacy	650	0.742	0.000** S

** *Significant at 1% level*

It is inferred from the above table that the p value is lesser than 0.01 and hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It shows that there is significant positive correlation exists between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers. The Pearson correlation co-efficient for self-efficacy and emotional intelligence was found as 0.742 which indicates that both variables are strongly positively correlated.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

Correlation analysis showed the existence of statistically significant strong positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers who have teaching experience of 5 years and below 5 years. And also statistically significant moderate positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers who have teaching experience of above 5 years was apparent. The correlation analysis also showed the significant strong positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence of school teachers. These findings are in consensus with the results of previous research studies relating to relationship between self-efficacy and emotional

intelligence (Yingying Wu, 2018; J. Parameswari, 2013; Mohammad, 2015; Moutan, Alexandre et al., 2013; Shaukat, Sadia, 2016). But, on the contrary, Rast&Tourani (2012) reported that there was no significant difference among male and female job satisfaction. Regarding the findings of the study particularly the significant positive correlation between emotional intelligence and self-efficacy, it seems that attention to emotional intelligence is very effective and valuable in improving self-efficacy of school teachers. Specifically school teachers high in emotional intelligence might be better able to regulate their teaching efficiency. The present study reveals that school teachers should have emotional intelligence for better self-efficacy. Teachers emotions are inextricably linked to teachers' well being, identity and emotion management in teaching. The ways in which emotions are managed by teachers often relate to the culture of teaching [9]. Research has showed that teachers' positive emotions like satisfaction and enjoyment are positively related to teachers' motivation, self-efficacy, innovation and commitment in teaching. While negative teachers' emotions are negatively related to these sources of teacher effectiveness. Thus Hargreaves said "good teaching is charged with positive emotion"[24]. Teachers who demonstrate emotionally intelligent behaviour in the classroom are more effective in achieving the academic goals they have set for themselves. Bandura and others have found that an individual's self-efficacy plays a major role in how goals, tasks, and challenges are approached. Emotional intelligence develops the knowledge and skills needed for teachers to create a classroom climate that can calm learners down [15]. Referring to the significant strong positive correlation between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence, the results of the study may be utilized in emphasizing emotional literacy and emotional intelligence in the curriculum of teacher education. As it has been proved in the study that emotional intelligence is positively related with self-efficacy of school teachers. Further researcher can consider its finding for future studies. Through personal counseling, teachers can be made aware that how low self-efficacy can contribute to their teaching learning problems in classroom setting and how becoming more emotional intelligent can overcome their tribulations during the classroom teaching learning process.

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